

OPERATIONAL TECHNOLOGY THREATS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES AND POSSIBLE SOLUTION

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Abstract— This particular research will involve proper analysis of several active threats about the operational technology existing within a number of various countries that are developing. The research will be depicting several issues that are mostly faced by some developing countries and will also comprise some recommendations that will help a lot in the mitigation of various recognised threats related to operational technology. The literature review will be comprising several resources that will be directly related to the key topic of research. The study will be capable of bringing out all of the various outcomes that are actually expected. This study will also involve a gap in the literature that will show all of the gaps that will be present in this study. A section of methodology comprises the opted research design, research philosophy, research approach, method of data collection, inclusion and exclusion criteria, analysis of data, and even the associated ethical issues. Lastly, there is a proper conclusion and also some recommendations for this study of research.

I. INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

Background of the Study

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is considered conjunction of all those technologies that blurs the prevalent lines between the physical and the digital worlds that come under cyber-physical systems or networks [1]. The awareness of operational technology and the severe and complicated infrastructure system and its security are rising. The path towards the protection and securing of operational technology systems is quite developed but requires proper watchfulness and understanding of the need to build the security. The very capability for implementing the security solutions that deliver quite a lot of perceptibility and control of the real-world awareness of the circumstance becomes the differentiators that help conduct safer and efficient operations. In a fast-changing world that is highly commercialised, important competitive advantage can be created with improved automation. OT networks operated independently in the past, which was entirely separated from the IT system in the same company [2]. However, data flow across the systems from customers to the manufacturers is essential as the data access in an operational technology network can affect everything from energy production to the output, thereby allowing the organizations to respond to the customer demands with greater efficiency [3].

Problem Statement

With every possible interlinking and the resulting extension of the operating systems comes an added risk to the automated operational technology. Therefore, with the addition of every new function, there comes new risk. Whenever any system goes online, it is bound to become a probable target. Hackers are pretty quick nowadays and are very efficient in finding out all the details by taking advantage of the vulnerabilities. It cannot be denied that new threats evolve as soon as the counter technology for eradicating the previous threats is built [4]. All these issues become more prevalent in the developing countries, which are very new in applying these rules; therefore, how a developed country handles this is far different from a developing country. This implements an active network more complex than ever. However, this is important in bringing about and creating defense against hackers and protecting the systems from any impending structural damage [5].

Research Aims and Objectives

Research Aim:

The research aims at analyzing the threats to operational technology that exists in developing countries. The research will help understand the various issues that the developing countries face and will throw enough light into the recommendations to mitigate the recognized operational technology threats.

Research Objectives:

The research objectives are as follows:

- To identify the operational threats of technology
- To analyze and understand the impact of operational technology threats in the developing countries
- To recommend ways that will help in mitigation of the identified issues about operation and technology

Research Questions

- The research questions are as follows:
- What are the operational threats of technology?

- What is the likely impact of operational technology threats in developing countries?
- What are ways in which the identified issues on operation and technology can be mitigated?

Thesis Statement

Developing countries have different dynamics that can alter the perception and sometimes overlook cybersecurity conveying the attacks' potentials by operational technology. Therefore, this specific document's objective is to comprehend the application of the developing countries' operational technologies and provide an overview of how they can protect themselves from such threats.

Research Rationale

Many of the original operational technology (OT) systems retuning the automotive manufacturing were not built, considering security to be the most important, due to negligible security risk in the past. These systems were said to consist of equipment that is separated initially entirely from all the other networks. However, the intermingling or the unison of IT and OT combined with the newer IoT has yielded new attack vectors previously not present. Thus, total automation aims at running and maintaining structures in various fields. Using systems such as and Industrial Control Systems (ICS) decreases the necessity for human interference. Human participation is required, much of which can be done remotely [6]. Therefore, this research will delve deeper into the threats and suggest remedies that the developing countries can understand and minimize threats.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

The specific chapter of the concerned thesis study accomplishes the predominant background literature on the concerned research topic. The United Nations points out the richest and developed countries with the highest per capita income as the most developed and upgrading countries. There is a massive introduction of the operational technology in the developing countries, which in turn includes some threats to the structure of the developing countries [7].

The review in a systematic way of the specific study has been discriminated in this section of the concerned study, with the theoretical framework's adoption at the end of the study for the proper clarification of the study.

Concept of Operational Technologies

Operational technology has now become the most common word on global parameters. Operational technology simply can be said as the OT. It signifies the plenty of computers and monitors or the alteration of the physical state of a specific

system. This also includes controlling the structure of the system for a control network of a power station for the execution of the rail system [8].

As today the various physical devices become more intelligent day by day, there is seen a rising trend towards adopting operational technologies in most of the fields. The actual concept of OT provides most of the wireless connectivity. This, in turn, provides immense betterment in the field of administrative works. This provides the administrator to control the whole work remotely with the use of operational technologies. The operational technology poses some malware, control of access, identification of the management, and many other security challenges faced by the IT [9]. The critical vulnerabilities that are found in operational technology can dispense the crucial structure at risk. This can cause a life or death situation if it is not addressed at the proper time. The operational technology system manages and monitors the industrial process's assets and the various works regarding the manufacturing of the types of equipment needed for industrial purposes. Operational technology plays a vital role in developing countries. Now the globe's development becomes more dependent on technological tools and techniques [10]. Operation technology is one of these concepts that are highly effective in the administrative workplace. OT concept is highly effective and has various implications in different fields.

Difference between IT and OT

Figure 1: The difference between IT and OT [11]

The operational technology monitors and manages the industrial process assets and helps in the manufacturing purposes of pieces of equipment required in the industrial field. Operational technology in the concept and the implication can last longer than the concept and the implication of information technology or the IT service. Information technology is the concept that can specifically evaluate as the implication of electricity in the various factories, the systems of the transpiration, buildings, and in the utility industry [12]. The critical evaluation of operational

technology is the managing and monitoring ability and the controlling ability of the physical device remotely. There are also some crucial differences between operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT).

Operational technology exists longer in the field of technology than information technology. More precisely, it can be said that information technology is the concept that is used in various fields. On the other hand, operational technology is the concept that keeps on ruining both the software and the hardware. The fundamental concept of operational technology and information technology are separated from each other. IT is always a specific domain of the CIO [13]. Operational technologies have different priorities, and information technology has very different priorities. The vast range of differentiability measured between the concept of information technology and operational technology in the field of cybersecurity. From the IT perspective, data is the king concept whereas, the whole process is the king concept in organizational technology. The IT has gateways everywhere, whereas; in the OT field, there are very few gateways. IT concept is fully dynamic. On the other hand, the OT concept is entirely deterministic. These are the most important differences between the fundamental concept of operational technology and information technology [14].

Available Operational Technologies and Types

The implication of the operational technology is increasing mentioned by the staff and employees of cybersecurity. The new upcoming industries' model's infrastructure system becomes more digitalized and more complex in day-to-day lifestyle. The concept of OT and its various implication is now required in many critical cases [15].

There are various types of operational technologies available in the market structure. One of the primary forms of critical security perspective is the Industrial Control System or ICS. The OT is considered an umbrella that can manage and monitor various forms of systems [16]. It also controls a broad range of industrial processes. The comprehensive control system of operational technology includes SCADA systems. That is Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition and the DCS systems. These all are run based on different programming languages. It also includes PLCs and RTUs. The concept of human-machine interface is also included in this specific study of operational technology.

This also includes several pieces of machinery and the pieces of equipment that are needed for the computing of the firms and various industrial purposes. This also includes the PLM system, the applications of MES, the systems regarding the automation of the safety and security, along with the management system regarding the building constructions [17].

Geopolitical Influence

Emerging the technologies like artificial intelligence and big data, and 5G telecommunication is crucial to financial services. This helps in underpinning new goods and transfer

measures of the operational processes. These primary technologies and different types of equipment, and various systems are used in the monitoring and measurement of the operational technology. The usage of operational technology also depends upon the process of various industries. These innovations are the most fundamental concept for the rising geopolitical rivalry [18].

Political Forecasts

Politics can hugely influence the acceptance of new technologies. The environment regarding the political atmosphere is considered the least predictable among all circumstances. Sometimes the political factor dominates the technological empowerment in the social structure. Operational technology (OT) helps announce the many political factors in the economy [19].

Current Conflicts

Rather than endurance of the significant Security operational technology (OT) breach that affects various confidentiality of the government along with various operations. The companies should consider these required actions to reduce various conflicts and mistrust OT while increasing ICS security at the same time. IT and OT structure have many conflicts.

Solutions

Research and Development

The research and development help in the growth process of the operational technology (OT). The research and development are perfect the process by which the system of Operational technology (OT) works to reach new knowledge that helps the researchers and every person use and create new technology, goods, and services, systems that for using and the selling purposes. The goal is achieved very easily and most often to add to the company's bottom line [20]. It refers to various innovative activities that corporations or governments undertake along with various companies in developing the new services or goods or improving the existing services or goods.

Available Solutions

Get various strategic alignments in operational technology (OT) at the highest levels:

This is an essential concept regarding the solution of the specific happening. This step takes complete responsibility for the issues [21].

Coordination of the joint task force by the researcher in operational technology (OT):

This is the second helpful step to be initiated by the researchers. There must a joint task force for the smooth operation of the concept. This should take place for the structural development.

Develop pilot projects structure in operational technology (OT) and a governing structure:

One of the first things of the joint cyber security task force process can implement to identify various pilot projects that both groups IT and OT can work on together. The researcher's task force can compile a list of various critical ICS assets that must be implemented and begin to assess what needs to be done [22].

Economic Repercussions

The society and the technology: The most critical case study of society's influence and the economic structure in technology. Technology helps in the overall growth of society. This involves the implication of operational technology (OT).

Consumer expectation: The essential part is technology always tries to reach the customer expectation. Technology reaches consumer satisfaction undoubtedly. The man is the inventor of the technology. High expectation causes the change in the technology [23].

Social changes: Some changes happen due to the implication of technology in economic structure. These types of social changes are not even suitable always. The enormous technological implication reduces the animal from the economic construction.

Possible Threats

OT security starts with various assessments of risk factors regarding cybersecurity. Threats are becoming very regular in this particular structure. The three components are there regarding the risk factors. These three steps of the assessment are:

The step regarding collection: This particular step includes the method manual or automated to collate the network data and identify the vulnerable devices. This also includes the various network parameters [24].

The step regarding analysis: The next step is analysis. This denotes the analysis of the collated data for the establishment of an operational technology framework. This would surely help to construct to adhere to maintain the standard of the industry. This is the most critical step of the study.

The step regarding projection: The last step is regarding the Projection of the assessment that includes real-time parameters for alerting. The audit of the policy and the procedure is the most crucial step that involves reviewing and auditing the operational technology (OT) of the cybersecurity policies [25].

Future Outlook

For the future outlook the researcher's concept of some regarding steps of the security in the network system, the

Security in the endpoint system, the Security in clouding, the data security, the intelligence security system, the vulnerable management system, and the continuity in the field of business [26].

Present Threats

Some threats are observed regarding the concept of operational technology (OT) of the cybersecurity policies. The present threats are explained below.

Lack of Test Environments: Operational technologies (OT) have different maturity level in contrast with Information Technology and one of the biggest challenge or threats is absence or lack of test environments. R&D and simulation is expensive in a way that industries still cannot afford to have such environment in place for the test purpose only.

Cultural difference between IT and OT: In the environment, we use culture of Engineers similar to IT and they care most about reliability and safety, fault tolerance, consistency and longevity. Engineers make sure that there is a stability when making changes in the OT environment. We need to define the optimum culture to manage the OT.

Air gapping: Operational technologies (OT) are far more separated from the concept of information technology (IT). This happens in the concept of air gapping. It is foremost essential for the regulation of the audit. Also, it scans these air gaps to maintain operational technology (OT) policies for ensuring connectivity [27].

Training: There is a severe lack in this section. These lacks are often seen in industries. This happens when the employees are not given adequate and proper knowledge for maintaining good OT (operational technology) security practices in the field of cybersecurity [28].

Incident response and planning regarding recovery: The various important Industries often fail to recover the critical document and methods regarding the critical backups. This also structures the happening of the poorest incident in case of the factors regarding outages.

Segmentation in the network: the various important industries need to be utilized the zone of the OT (Operational Technologies) systems and conduit concepts when dealing with OT security in the field of cyber section. They can limit the vulnerable incidents by the imposition of proper plans and controlling the access to specific zones of the OT (Operational Technologies) systems [29].

Awareness lack: There is seen a lack of awareness in the cybersecurity system about the OT security vulnerabilities. This is why companies are not ready to invest in protecting their OT (Operational Technologies) systems and the production of the various devices.

Literature Gap

For this particular case study, the literature review has been executed to be constructed at the extreme depth of the study with utmost possibility. However, this study has specific gaps that could not be filled due to some happenings due to happenings of circumstantial reasons [30]. At the initial stage, there were some problems due to the gathering of sufficient data required for the chosen period regarding the particular topic that has been considered. Besides this, the specific research area posed some aftermath on covering up the required data for the specific study analysis [31]. To avoid the issues regarding the accessibility of the concerning issues of the certain topic were posed in the pathway of gathering the secondary data of the study. The solution of the changing and the modifying title for this particular research is adopted. These are the most fundamental concepts of the literature gap that is faced during the research regarding the concerned topic.

Summary

This particular research provides awareness regarding the availability and the implication of the operational technologies and the specific challenges in the various developing countries. This study covers the different threats from the several developing countries about the structure of operational technologies. As research goes on, it is also found that is even challenging for specific developed countries will take some more time. This study focuses on the political and current conflicts [32]. Along with the available economic solution of the study concept, this study also includes the future outwork and the present threats regarding the implementation of the operational technologies in developing countries. The last section of the study includes the gaps in the literature faced during the research study [33]. This study will surely help as the thesis paper for the upcoming researches regarding this specific topic.

III. METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The research relating to the operational technology threats in developing countries and its possible solution requires a well-defined research methodology that effectively identifies, selects, processes, and analyzes information regarding the topic. The methodology enables the researcher to critically estimate the overall reliability and validity by clearly explain all the necessary steps for data collection and analysis. It constitutes research design, philosophy, approach, data collection method, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data analysis, and ethical issues.

Research Design

The overall strategy chosen to study and analyze the different components in a study is the research design. Primarily, there

are three methodologies in research design such as explanatory, exploratory, and descriptive. Explanatory research significantly connects ideas to understand the case, which requires adequate investigation. Exploratory research studies the previous researches on the topic to develop deeper insights [34]. The descriptive approach defines the characteristics, population and undergoes a critical analysis of the problem, both qualitative and quantitative. The descriptive approach is followed in the paper as critical analysis is effective for finding possible solutions.

Research Philosophy

Data collected in research is based on a particular belief regarding the phenomena is known as research philosophy. Commonly, research philosophy is categorized into four parts, interpretivisms, positivism, realism, and pragmatism. The interpretivism approach is practiced in social science research as it tries to understand the social world and does not involve any actual investigation and analysis [35]. The positivist approach gives shape to individuals by understanding human behavior. The positivism approach believes that society shapes the individual as the social world works objectively. The realism approach is based on the reality of own mind following assumptions in the empirical investigation as real cases follow structures, processes, and entities [36]. Pragmatism is associated with facts and follows a mixed methodology structure. The current research follows the positivism approach for qualitatively study the operational technology threats in developing countries.

Research Approach

The research approach investigates the plans and procedures followed in the research. It is classified under the top-down and the bottom-up approach. The top-down approach studies the research from a broad perspective to a narrow one, and the bottom-down approach follows the opposite manner. The paper follows the top-down approach to broaden the perspective. Accordingly, the paper follows deductive and inductive approaches [37]. The deductive approach aims to develop a theory relating to the topic, and the inductive approach follows existing theories for research. Developing theories are complicated and require adequate research, which may not give effective results. Thus, the paper follows a deductive approach to use existing theories and find a suitable solution for the operational technology threats in developing countries.

Data Collection Method

The method of collecting data in research depends on the type of data to be collected for the research. There are two types of data sources: primary and secondary where primary data is collected by researchers through interviews and surveys; researchers already collect secondary data. As the paper follows the deductive approach, secondary data is more

effective, taken from authentic sources, government websites, and peer-reviewed journal articles. The collected data can be either qualitative or quantitative. Qualitative data are descriptive and immeasurable, and quantities data are about quantities or numbers [38]. To study the operational threats in developing countries, quantitative data is inadequate to explain the causes. As a result, the paper follows qualitative research concerning secondary data sources. Thus, the method of collecting data is peer-reviewed journal articles, authentic websites, and books.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria help select the data sources that need to be chosen, and exclusion criteria help to reject the eliminated data sources. The inclusion criteria for studying the operational technology threats are the data from books, peer-reviewed journal articles, authentic government websites of developing countries from 2010 to 2020 regarding operational technology problems. Exclusion criteria are data sources before 2010 and taken from developed countries. Websites that are inauthentic present quality information and having language, other than English.

Data Analysis

The current research undergoes data analysis in two ways—past literature and case study. Literature available on operational technology in developing countries is critically analyzed concerning the chosen period [39]. The case study takes account of several cases to reveal operational technology threats and analyze the outcomes. Based on outcomes, solutions are to be formed for effective research.

Ethical Issues

The research meets the ethical standards of the university and country. Information is taken from authentic sources that are critically reviewed. Sources are appropriately cited, and information is subjected to plagiarism. No person is harmed during the research, and the research is conducted following all the ethical practices.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Introduction

Security in the OT generally covers the controlling of the Security around Process Control Systems (PCS), Distributed Control Systems (DCS), and Supervisory Control and Acquisition of Data (SCADA) environments which are also thus combined referred to as Industrial Control Systems (ICS) perceiving into the environments. An environment involving the ICS can be as simply referring as the workstation of engineering that is being connected with the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), which is seen to be interfacing with

smaller sets of relays and meters or can be perceived as complexity into the as a high resistant system of distribution and the system that is distributed is thus involved into the commanding center that is managing thousands of devices of Industries across many sites. Thus, here in the assessment, a detailed study of the Security into OT fields has been reviewed, studying the varied aspects of the security in the OT and the varied challenges been faced by the Security of the OT. Beneficiaries have been added to the security fabric and several strategies for the operational methods are implemented

Thematic Analysis

OT Security

OT Security refers to the term that signifies the technological advances and the practicing method implemented to protect the people into the asset's formation and the information gathered. Monitoring and controlling the physical devices that start processing the underlying events. It starts initiation into the changes of the state into the system of OT enterprise. Solutions relating to the OT's Security involve a broader aspect of the relating technologies that could be adopted from the firewalls of the future generation. Information relating to the security and management of the event are thus implemented into the systems to identify the varied notions of accessing and management and various larger aspects [40]. Security of OT to the cyber world, in traditional ways, was not essential into the form as the systems of the OT are not connected with the availability of the internet. They do not incur the exposition of the threats into the outside world. Initiatives into the digital world have increased, and the OT and IT networks are thus made into converged [41]. Organizations are thus perceived to impose varied solutions into some of the specific points to address various specific issues related to the studied detail. Approaches to the OT's Security thus formulates in resulting into the matter of complexity of the network that does not be implemented in finding the solutions that cannot be able to incorporate solutions. Thus, the solutions do not incur the capability of sharing the information and thus be able to provide visibility in a full-fledged way.

Priority of OT Security

Organizations relating to the industries are thus rushing by taking advantage of the IT technologies into the technologies of operation. Working ambiance relating to the subject has been posing competitiveness. In the world of changing, systems that are interconnected and the analytics of the data, ICS, SCADA, sensors being intelligent, and IIOT are made in addition to manufacturing [42]. Increment into the efficiency that has been perceived caters to the addition of benefits into this sector. In the sphere of the infrastructure, risks are observed that are countered by the imposition of the shared data over OT's Security. Thus, the security context paves the

way for offering a portfolio into the sphere of the Operational Technology solutions of security that would help the industries. It would also act as a beneficiary towards building up an intensive environment and thus monitors and provides security to the preferred networks. The also incur the availability of the protecting the endpoints and thus indulge in delivering several services relating to the cybersecurity issues.

Major OT and ICS Concerns

Information Technology refers to the field of study related to computer technology factors, which thus pacifies to involve both the notions of the hardware and the software. The vital distinction between the OT and the IT is that devices involved in the OT control the whole of the world of physical strata, whereas the systems of IT manage the data [43]. Several concerning behaviorisms are being perceived through the OT and ICS, which are elaborated into this specified context.

Several risks are seen to have been imposed on the environment. Risk into the procedures of mitigation strategies and are also supported by several remedial solutions, which are thus perceived with the patching into the limitation [44]. They have been very hard that has been used in the testing procedures in the context of the environment of the production. The lower amount of visibility involved in the assets, analytics procedures, and various data associated with the data thus impose huge risk threats over the environment.

Security Skills are thus seen to perceive with limitation. It is generally conferred that the teams of OT don't support or acquire the knowledge about the security proceedings. Processes that are involved in the system of the IT teams also do not support the view of the operation processes. The gap in the skill critically thus is added in contributing to the vulnerability that has been evolved into security issues.

Disrupted coordination's are evolved into operational procedures. Attacks onto the periphery of the cybercrime on the grounds of SCADA and the ICS can impose influential behavior over the safeties, availability and the several issues of reliability [45]. Prediction about the workers, operations involved, and the chain of value results in the depiction of issues that can be referred to as the environment's catastrophic nature.

Complain against the protection of data is thus involved. Regulatory imposition of the government continuously is paving to grow as the attacks relating to the cyber attacks are on the verge of the increment [46]. Attacks relating to the cyber security issues not been observed that they are only with the frequency, however with the severe condition too. Such dynamic changes that are being perceived over the environment poses to influence in the development of varied changes related to the operational behavior into the studied area.

Benefits of Security Fabric

Security fabric determines three types of beneficiaries in terms of Visibility, Control, and Continuous Monitoring.

In discovering any of the devices found to be attached to the IT- OT network, determining the degree of trust to the specific issue is what is essential. Continuously monitoring it helps bring the level of trust upgraded [47]. Defining the attack's surface, ensuring the active devices, and profiling based on traffic should have to be ensured. Assurances of the visibility of the traffic in respect of the actions that are in action are required. Thus, teams being involved in the OT security allow in dictating traffic, protocols maintained, applications, ports, and the varied services. Points that are enforced into the environment ensure the protection into the north-south and west-east level.

Dependencies upon the system of OT and the various subsystem are to carry out the proceedings of the job. Authentication regarding the varied multi-level factors ensures that the people are assigning to have permissions and access properly. Segmentation into the network and several micro segmenting procedures thus pave a way to layered and approach levelling within the control zones [48]. Quarantine into the automated version helps in preventing internal damage.

Analysis of continuing behaviors into the networks of OT thus helps in providing the teams to gather intelligence about the varied threats that are known or the fact that is not known. Thus, a tool of security paves a way to log out, to report, dependent upon analytically, and thus evaluate the collected activities within the observed system [49]. It provides security of information and management of events and maintains the orchestration into the automated security, and the capabilities of the responses are gathered too. The user's perspective acquires security of the OT insights and the analysis of the behavior is carried out with the procedure of assessing threats that also play a role in ensuring in protecting continuously.

Challenges to OT Security

There has been observed that several challenges are defined within the periphery of the Security of the OT. Risk assessment into the OT infers about a percent of 74 percent. The percentage of the companies that do not have any specification of the policies ranging from the OT incurs about 78% in terms of the policies [50]. Among the respondents, more than one-third that has been reported worries about the following challenges of securities of OT. Third parties thus perceive to incur a lag over security expertise that has been needed in assisting with technology that has been converged and the Internet of Things (IoT) being Sensitive; otherwise, the data of confidentiality would be leaked [51]. Businesses that are developed do not have the recommendation of implementing a security-specified plan of response that is related to the OT. It is none the secret that OT has been producing threatening issues over the development. According to security of latest, Skybox imposes Vulnerability issues and thus claims by threatening the reports that are in trend. There is an increment into the risk that is hampering the growth of surface attacks being brought by the likes of the internet of things (IoT) of industrial issues and OT networks.

Attacks are observed into the OT thus continued to climbing, with an increment of 10% between the year 2017 and 2018 [52]. The attacks have been ranged in the motive and is impacted that, the outbreak of Wanna Cry has hit Taiwanese Semiconductor Company of Manufacturing (TSMC) was a vital example showing how the effectiveness of tool of cybercriminal namely ransomware. Threats all over the nation-state and exposure to several internalities thus create the perfect storm of cyber-attack that is imposing havoc influence over a network and the company's bottom line. Stuxnet Company also faced similar damage in the year 2010.

Strategies for Operation

Assessing the risk is an essential factor. The assessment of the risk starts effectivity into the security program. Visibility should thus be ensured over the OT's environment and must be observing the assets of vulnerability. Operational strategies should also be marking the engagement of the plans and strategies among the prospect of the complaint and assessments of vulnerability. Developmental policies of the government and the requirement must also be fulfilled in the highlighted point.

The operational activities must support protection. Thus, operational activities must be conveyed over in carrying out the efficiency in carrying out the desired objectives into the implementation of the effectiveness of the OT's Security. Discoveries into the data, analyzing and classifying, several networks and designs into the endpoint security and their implementation should have to be introduced into the sector [53]. Deployment of the identity and building it can thus result in accessing the solution to the management issues. The team should also participate in the designing and deploying of an OT SOC that protects the operations.

Operations management must be ensured in order to run the operational management smoothly and efficiently. If there is perceived any of the attacks, it should have been better in reacting to incorporate the plan of response into the specified area of OT. Thus, managing the alerting issues and reducing the positives of falseness is associated with the managed security services [54]. Development of the security service relating to the OT has enormous responses over the land with the playbooks. This thus contributes to helping to focus on the improving paradigm of the operations of the security.

Summary

Security of OT is thus a software or a hardware device that helps in the detection or thus causes to incur a transformation through implementing the directly monitored processor that could be implemented over the controlled devices' procedure [55]. It also evolves several inclusions of the processes and the generated events into the system of the enterprise. The respondents of the raised issue that involves around more than one third of the people who are being worried about the several challenges associated with the Security issues. Parties of the third-order often suffer from the issue of lacking

expertise in the security aspect. They are in the requirement to assist the technology that is converged and the Internet of Things Sensitive. This could be the fact that the secured data could thus be leaked. Priorities of the securities are driven mainly by the responses of the assets that are found in nature. Into the IT realm, the most criticality element and the targeted attacks are thus implemented into the inclusion of equipment and the process [56]. Priorities of Security are thus diversely based upon the basis of the differences.

Thus, the security of the OT is important and is commonly been implemented in protecting the systems of industries and from the attacks of technology in the operation. Operational Security Technology thus paves a way for protecting and controlling the infrastructure that are critical and thus it comprises of the stations at power firms, networks in the transportation and the application into the cities that are smart.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

It can be concluded that Security within the OT generally covers the specific control of security around the PCS, DCS, and even the respective environments of SCADA. Several kinds of risks are found to be countered by imposing the data shared over the OT security. OT or the Operational Technology will offer several security solutions to various industries as it acts like a specific beneficiary towards properly building up a specific environment that will be intensive to several assets and thus can be monitoring and also offering security to the networks are preferred. This will also be incurring the particular availability of the protection of endpoints and thus will be indulging indirectly offering several various services which are directly related to the issues of cybersecurity. Security fabric is possessing several benefits towards the Security of OT.

Linking with Objectives

The research has offered a lot of awareness about the particular implication and the availability of OT or Operational Technologies and different kinds of threats and challenges within several countries that are developing. This research study has covered all of the various kinds of threats from several countries developing about the OT structure. The research has focused more on the various conflicts, which are recent as well as political. It has involved the outwork of the upcoming future and some of the current threats about implementing several operational technologies within all of the countries that are found to be developing. To solve all of the threat-related problems associated with OT, OT security has been significantly prioritized. It has been found that several various benefits are offered by the security fabric, which is known to be determined three kinds of beneficiaries upon the particular terms of visibility, controlling as well as continuous monitoring. Hence, it can be said that the research

is capable of covering all of the key objectives of the study for bringing out appropriate outcomes which are expected.

Recommendation

One must be ensuring the management of various operations for adequately running the operational management smoothly and efficiently. If an attack is perceived, it must be better indirectly reacting to incorporate the response plan into the OT area. There must be proper management of various issues that are alerting. Doing this and reducing all of the positives of falseness is directly associated with various security services that are appropriately managed. It must be remembered that risk assessment is a significant factor. There must be proper security programs, and one must also be ensuring visibility over the particular OT environment and seeing various vulnerability assets. All of the various operational strategies must be marking plans and strategies of engagement among the specific prospect of the vulnerability assessment. These recommendations will be very much helpful for obtaining better OT security.

Future Scopes

Eventually, OT and IT security will be overlapping as both of them will be dealing with the various fundamentals of the encryption of data, authentication, quality, and reliability. This is because it is found that about 80% of the issues related to security that OT faces are almost similar to IT, while 20% are very much unique, not to be anyhow ignored and critical.

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